

The Coupling Constants Series and Galaxies Rapid Formation

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Abstract:

By analyzing the new framework, which regard bosonic propagations as net curvatures on a varying Lorenz manifold, $s = (M, g)$ with signature $(3,1)$, invoked stationary by EL operator. Alongside the result given by the coupling constants series it than becomes possible to construct process in which large fermionic clusters have formed, we can reason for rapid rate of their formation by two arguments: the first is coupling constants series and endless coupling terms stronger than the gravitational, in fact gravity plays no rule in cluster formations at all, due to its spin. The second, the fact that bosons are regarded to be net curvature on the varying Lorenz manifold, comparing with fermion clusters which no curvature is allowed due to demanding stationarity.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.0)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.01)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.11)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.12)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.13)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i > 0 \quad (1.15)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.16)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.17)$$

$$(3) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(5)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.18)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(\gamma)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.19)$$

The overall construction now will be used to reason the fast formation of galaxies. Since fermions are regarded in this framework to be arbitrary variations to vanish by discretizing and partitioning δg given by equation (1.14). In other words, no curvature is allowed and none appears of fermion cluster. Now, since bosonic propagations are isomorphic to prime number of variations that cannot vanish into matter, they add up to a positive summation or a net curvature given by equation (1.15), and so they cause fermions to cluster. Since there are infinite amount of bosonic fields after the electric coupling term, and they are all spin one fields, i.e. they have long range effect unlike gravity which is short range due to spin two, the end result is endless succession of clustering in a very rapid rate. The construction of the coupling constant series and the insight that made it work, that bosonic fields are net curvature on the Lorentz manifold allow us to reason in an elegant way concerning the formation of large-scale fermionic clusters, i.e. galaxies could accrue. In contrast to GR and Einstein theory, it's not matter that bends the bosonic rays, it's the bosonic rays which deflect and effect matter as they are net curvature on the manifold. It is given by the coupling constants series and equation (1.13), (1.14), that is how nature really works.

Those Bosonic are generated by the same element, the Majestic (3), proven to be the electron. Since almost all Bosonic fields (excluding the strong interaction) are generated by the same element, this element than creating an infinite cyclic group, described by equation (1.19), and so we were able to prove that the photon is a closed cycle, in agreement with other modern theories of physics. Two things make the construction solid, the first is the infinite sequence of immensely stronger interactions than the gravitational, the second is the idea of bosonic fields as net curvature which allowed us to build the coupling constants series in the first place.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)